

Table 2. Grain yield of CR1018 as influenced by transplanting date, seedling age, and spacing. Cuttack, India, 1984 wet season.

Spacing (cm)	Seedling age (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)			Mean yield (t/ha)
		15 Jul	15 Aug	15 Sep	
15 × 15	30	5.5	4.9	2.8	4.4
	60	3.9	4.0	3.4	3.8
20 × 15	30	5.2	3.5	2.7	3.8
	60	5.5	4.1	3.3	4.3
20 × 20	30	5.3	4.0	2.6	4.0
	60	5.2	3.9	3.2	4.1
25 × 20	30	5.4	3.9	2.2	3.8
	60	5.3	3.8	2.9	4.0
Mean		5.2	4.0	2.9	
LSD (0.05)	main plot (planting dates)	=		1.0	
LSD (0.05)	subplot (spacing × seedling age)	=		ns	
LSD (0.05)	for comparing planting dates (spacing × seedling age)	=		1.1	
LSD (0.05)	for comparing (spacing × seedling age) within a planting date	=		0.8	

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Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Response of BR3 rice to duckweed (*Lemna minor*) application

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Duckweed is a minute, diploid spore-producing, vascular, free-floating aquatic plant that contains around 4% N. It grows abundantly in stagnant

water in Bangladesh, especially during the monsoon. We studied its use as an organic N source for rice.

Duckweed was grown in earthen pots 56.41 cm in diameter (1 m²), filled with 60 kg air-dried soil and 72 liters of water. Composition (oven-dried basis) of the duckweed was 4.2% N; 2.3% P; 3.02% K; and 29.64% organic C.

Two seedlings of rice variety BR3 were planted in pots containing 10 kg soil and fertilized with 35 kg P and 33 kg K/ha. Soil was silty loam with pH 5.2, 0.84% organic C, 80 kg 2M KCl

extractable N/ha, 18.4 kg Olsen's reagent extractable P/ha, and 134 kg neutral N ammonium acetate extractable K/ha.

Treatments were 5 t fresh duckweed/ha = 833 kg oven-dried duckweed/ha, and 5.0, 2.5, 1.9, and 1.43 t oven-dried duckweed/ha and 2 combinations of oven-dried duckweed + urea. Each treatment was replicated three times in a completely randomized design.

Incorporating 5 t oven-dried duckweed/ha increased grain yields 52% and straw yields 50% (see table). Combined 20 kg urea N/ha + 1.43 t duckweed/ha increased grain yields 62% and straw yields 67%. Urea applied at 80 kg N/ha increased grain yields 50% and straw yields 44%. Oven-dried duckweed at 5 t/ha was better than urea at 80 kg N/ha.

N uptake was greater in the treatments where urea was applied. □

Yield of and N uptake by BR3 rice as affected by application of duckweed and urea.

t/ha	Duckweed applied		Urea applied (kg N/ha)	Yield (g/pot)		N uptake (mg/pot)
	kg N/ha	As % weight of 10 kg soil		Grain	Straw	
0	0	0	0	8.51	7.21	140.4
5.00 ^a	35	0.250	0	9.80	7.31	165.1
5.00	210	0.250	0	13.00	10.82	279.4
2.50	105	0.125	0	12.01	8.55	235.9
1.90	80	0.095	0	12.40	10.00	251.1
1.43	60	0.070	0	11.94	9.77	225.6
1.43	60	0.070	20	13.80	12.11	318.3
0.95	40	0.048	40	13.50	11.28	313.1
0.00	0	0.000	80	12.80	10.42	327.8
LSD (P=0.01)				2.36	1.11	

^aFresh duckweed incorporated 7 d before transplanting.

Using iron pyrite to increase nitrogen efficiency in rice under sodic conditions

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N efficiency in rice under sodic conditions is reduced because of heavy